

HEALING FROM THE UNDERGROUND IN RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS: THERMAL SPRING TREATMENT

Keywords

Rheumatoid Arthritis,

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ABSTRACT

Rheumatoid arthritis is a systemic, inflammatory, chronic progressive autoimmune disease that causes pain, swelling, heat increase, and stiffness in the joints due to inflammation in the synovium within the joint. It is one of the most common chronic inflammatory diseases globally. It is reported to affect 0.1–2.0% of the world's population. The primary goal in treating rheumatoid arthritis is to minimize pain, prevent possible complications, and improve the quality of life for patients. Treatment options include non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), glucocorticoids containing steroid hormones, disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs, biological agents, nanotechnology, oral tolerance, gene therapy, bone marrow transplantation, liposomes, superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles, and iron nanoparticles. However, pharmacological treatments alone are often insufficient. For this reason, many patients seek non-pharmacological therapies alongside conventional pharmacological treatments. One of these therapies is thermal spring therapy. Treating with thermal waters is considered an ancient medical practice and is regarded as one of the oldest medical interventions. Thermal spring therapy has been used since antiquity, primarily for rheumatic and musculoskeletal system disorders, as well as for the treatment of many diseases. This review provides information about the use of thermal spring therapy, a non-pharmacological method used as an adjunct to pharmacological treatment in the management of rheumatoid arthritis.

INTRODUCTION

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a systemic, inflammatory, chronic progressive and autoimmune disease characterized by swelling and tenderness in synovial joints, which can cause systemic complications such as cardiovascular and pulmonary disorders, damage to cartilage and bone, functional losses and premature death.¹ Rheumatoid arthritis has historically caused significant disability, morbidity, and premature death, but the clinical outcomes of the disease have improved greatly over the past 25 years.² It is one of the most common chronic inflammatory diseases in the World.¹ It has been reported to affect 0.1-2.0% of the population worldwide.³ In Turkey, the prevalence of the disease was determined as 0.56%. This disease occurs most often between the ages of 20-45.¹ A higher incidence is observed in women, individuals with a family history, and smokers.⁴ Rheumatoid arthritis is considered a multifactorial disease where various genetic and environmental factors influence the prevalence of the disease across and within countries.³ Among the risk factors for rheumatoid arthritis, 60% are genetic and 40% are environmental factors. It has been determined that a significant portion of genetic risk factors are associated with human leukocyte antigens (HLA) located on chromosome 6.¹ Environmental factors include female gender, vitamin D deficiency, infectious agents, silica exposure, smoking, obesity, and microbiota alterations.⁵

The main purpose of rheumatoid arthritis treatment is to minimize or eliminate pain, prevent possible complications and increase the quality of life of patients. Treatment options for rheumatoid arthritis include nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), glucocorticoids containing steroid hormones, disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs, monoclonal antibodies,

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biological agents, nanotechnology, oral tolerance, gene therapy, bone marrow transplantation, liposomes, superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles and iron oxide.¹ Pharmacological treatments alone are not sufficient for the treatment of the disease. For this reason, many patients have sought non-pharmacological treatments in addition to medical treatments to reduce the symptoms they experience due to the disease and to reduce the disability caused by rheumatoid arthritis. One of the most commonly used non-pharmacological treatments for rheumatoid diseases in European countries is spa treatments.⁵

Treatment with thermal waters is an ancient art and is thought to be one of the oldest medical procedures. Throughout history, people have benefited from thermal waters in various ways, such as religious purification, relaxation, cleansing and treatment. Since diagnosing and treating diseases was a great effort for the physician in the ages when viruses and bacteria were not yet known, the potential of baths for preventive and protective medicine or treatment is extremely important in the ancient world where the ways of combating diseases were primitive and very limited.⁶ The word spa comes from the word 'Closed Hot Spring. Hot spring is defined as a place with hot (thermal) water. Hot spring is used to mean a hot spring where a facility has been established.⁷ Thermal spring treatment is also known as SPA treatment or balneotherapy. This treatment method can be defined as a 'stimulation-adaptation' treatment performed in a certain period of time and in a cure style by using hot mineral waters, gases and peloids from natural underground sources, with detailed methods and doses, in the form of bathing, drinking and inhalation treatments, repeated at regular intervals in a series.⁸ Spa treatment has been used since ancient times in the treatment of many diseases, especially rheumatic and musculoskeletal disorders⁹ Spa treatment includes many medical applications and spa resources include thermal and mineral waters, natural peloids (muds) and gases.^{10,11}

The effect of spa treatment on rheumatic diseases is the result of mechanical, thermal, chemical and immunomodulatory effects.¹² Mechanical effects are the effects of buoyancy, hydrostatic pressure and viscosity of water. These are also called immersion effects.⁸ Thermal effects; It creates an analgesic effect by providing warmth, muscle relaxation and increasing the pain threshold in nerve endings.¹² Again, activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary adrenal axis via the thermoregulation center in the hypothalamus with thermal

effect leads to increases and decreases in plasma norepinephrine, adrenocorticotrophic, and growth hormone levels. As a result, anti-edematous and anti-inflammatory effects have been observed in some rheumatological patients.⁸ Chemical effects; Depending on the temperature of the water during bathing, its chemical composition, the blood flow to the skin, the duration of bathing and other factors, some minerals and gases contained in it are also absorbed along with the water absorbed from the skin. Carbon dioxide (CO₂), hydrogen sulfide (H₂S), Radon (Rn) and sulfur are the main substances absorbed.¹² It has been stated that thermal baths and mud packs, especially those containing sulfur, have positive effects on the oxidant and antioxidant systems.⁸ In terms of immune modulatory effects, mild hyperthermia (38-38.5 0C) is thought to have an immune stimulant effect, while severe hyperthermia (>40 0C) has an immune suppressive effect. With the effect of hyperthermia, the immune system is activated with the increase in local skin temperature, and pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 β and IL-6 increase. At higher temperatures, the immune system is suppressed.¹²

Thermal Spring Treatment Applications in Rheumatoid Arthritis

Rheumatoid arthritis is a disease that begins at a young age in every society and increases in frequency and severity, especially in older ages, and requires patients to take medication for almost a lifetime. In the event of rheumatoid arthritis, the patient's quality of life deteriorates, he/she cannot lead a normal life due to pain and limited movement, and psychic disorders ranging from anxiety to depression are also added to the Picture.¹³

Thermal spring treatment for rheumatoid arthritis includes treatments traditionally performed in places where balneological resources are naturally found, combined with climatic factors, exercise practices, massage, rest, environmental change, social and psychological interaction.⁷ One of the most widely used non-pharmacological treatments for rheumatoid arthritis in European countries to improve the quality of life of patients is thermal spring treatment.⁵ Although most U.S. physicians are skeptical about the use of thermal spring therapy for rheumatoid arthritis, they support its use.¹⁴ At the same time, in the consensus recommendations of the Turkish Rheumatism Association for the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis, the use of thermal spring therapy as a non-pharmacological treatment of rheumatoid arthritis in Turkey

has been recommended.^{15,16} The benefits of thermal spring treatment include improving mobility and reducing stiffness and pain. These benefits may have a positive effect on rheumatoid arthritis symptoms, which may improve the quality of life of patients with rheumatoid arthritis. The increase in beta-endorphin produced by various spa treatment techniques has an analgesic and anti-spastic effect, which is particularly important in patients where pain is a common symptom, while hot stimuli can help increase the pain threshold at nerve endings by affecting muscle tone and pain intensity.⁵

It has been reported that symptoms decreased in long-term follow-up in rheumatoid arthritis patients who received thermal spring treatment.⁹ With thermal spring treatment, patients were observed to have significant improvements in joint stiffness, hand grip strength, pain, daily living activities and depressive disorders.⁸

In a study comparing sodium chloride, sulfurous hot spring water and mud pack applications with normal hot water applications in patients with rheumatoid arthritis, it was shown that while improvement was found in both groups, this improvement was temporary, but there was an increase in hand grip strength compared to the beginning in the group that received the hot spring and mud pack application. They stated that sulfurous thermal spring water reduced morning stiffness and the number of active joints in patients with rheumatoid arthritis in a three-month follow-up, increased hand grip strength, reduced pain, and that an analgesic effect could occur with the absorption of sulfur through the skin. It has been reported that sulfur thermal baths reduce the level of superoxide dismutase in patients with rheumatoid arthritis and thus have positive effects on the oxidant and antioxidant systems.⁸

Radon baths applied in addition to multimodal rehabilitation therapy including exercises, physiotherapy, occupational therapy and galvanic baths have been shown to have long-term beneficial effects, such as long-term improvements in pain intensity and reduced consumption of corticosteroids, NSAIDs or analgesics.¹⁷ When the effects of radon-carbon dioxide and artificial carbon dioxide water on pain intensity in patients with rheumatoid arthritis were compared, it was found that radon-carbon dioxide water was more effective.⁸ In another study, adding radon to carbon dioxide baths did not improve pain intensity at three months but did improve overall well-

being and pain at six months compared to carbon dioxide baths without radon.¹⁸

There seems to be evidence for the relevance and positive effects of thermal spring therapy in limiting the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, prostaglandins or even adipokines in patients with rheumatoid arthritis.⁵ Mud bath treatment induced a decrease in the circulating levels of prostaglandin E2 (PGE2), leukotriene B4 (LTB4), interleukin (IL)-1 β , tumor necrosis factor (TNF)- α and IL-6, which play a role in inflammation and chondrolysis seen in rheumatoid arthritis.¹⁹

It is thought that thermal spring treatment has the capacity to regulate and reduce oxidative status parameters in patients with rheumatoid arthritis and, in addition, may have an effect in reducing the main markers of bone and cartilage damage.⁵ Data from mouse models of rheumatoid arthritis have shown that different thermal spring treatments are effective in reducing pain, inflammation, and improving mobility, as well as reducing the expression of matrix-degrading enzymes and markers of oxidative stress damage.¹⁹ Another study noted positive effects on the quality of life of rheumatoid arthritis patients for both mineral baths and immersion in sand or mud. A multimodal, nonpharmacological thermal spring treatment intervention including radon therapy demonstrated significant improvements in pain at rest and on movement up to 9 months after treatment.²⁰

A study conducted with 50 rheumatoid patients investigated whether 2 weeks of thermal spring treatment in addition to normal pharmacological treatment had any beneficial effects in patients with rheumatoid arthritis. The total mineralization of the hot spring water is 3367 mg/L and it is saline water with a high sodium chloride concentration (1900 mg/L) and also contains relatively low calcium and magnesium concentration. It includes a daily salt thermal spring treatment session at 36-37 °C for 20 minutes, except on Sundays. As a result of the treatment, a statistically significant decrease in the number of swollen joints was observed in the second week compared to the initial level. In the general evaluation of the patient at 3 months, a trend was seen in favor of the treated group in terms of function and disease activity. Significant improvements were found in disease activity and in the patient in the thermal spring treatment.¹⁶

In a systematic review investigating the effectiveness of spa treatment in improving the quality of life of patients with

rheumatoid arthritis, it was mentioned that spa treatment sessions should be approximately 20 minutes long and at a water temperature between 35-38 °C, using natural mineral waters and mud enriched with elements, and each session should consist of immersing the whole body in these waters without moving the body and without doing any exercise. It has been suggested that hot sand baths can be used instead of mineral waters or even a combination of the two and that the total number of sessions should be 15, with the sessions being performed on consecutive days.⁵

Nursing Management in Thermal Spring Treatment in Rheumatoid Arthritis

The clinical presentation of rheumatoid arthritis is highly heterogeneous and systemic. It is not limited to joint inflammation alone. Symptoms such as pain, fatigue, morning stiffness, sleep disturbances or depression significantly affect patients' quality of life. Symptoms such as pain, fatigue, morning stiffness, sleep disturbances or depression significantly affect patients' quality of life. The European League Against Rheumatism (EULAR) has prepared recommendations for the role of nurses in the management of chronic inflammatory diseases, emphasising the optimisation of nurses' competences and skills as part of overall disease management. This model of care has been proven to contribute to reducing costs associated with rheumatic diseases. Nursing consultations have been shown to be effective in controlling disease activity and reducing the perceived impact in individuals with rheumatoid arthritis.²¹

Thermal spring treatment is used to supplement standard medical treatment, provide symptom control, and enhance the patient's well-being and care. Nurses should have sufficient and necessary knowledge, skills and equipment regarding the possible effects of spa treatment when used together with medical treatments or alone. In the study conducted with 100 nurses, 72% of the participants were informed about spa treatment, 50% found spa treatment effective and 20% thought it was as effective as medical treatment. Nurses believe that spa therapy treats pain in various painful conditions, provides relief, and should be used in patient care and treatment of rheumatoid arthritis.

CONCLUSION

The aim of thermal spring treatment is to improve joint range of motion in rheumatoid arthritis, relieve muscle spasms,

maintain or improve functional mobility, soothe pain and ultimately relieve patients' suffering and help them feel well. Thermal spring treatment is easier to apply than all other conventional medical methods. It is a treatment method with almost zero side effects. For thermal spring treatment to be effective, it is essential to continue pharmacological treatment. The increasing use of thermal spring treatment in rheumatoid arthritis improves the quality of life of patients. It is important for the nursing profession, which is directly involved in patient care, to have more knowledge about spa treatments in order to effectively educate patients about these treatments and in nursing care.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study.

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No

REFERENCES

1. Atan G. The Effect of Traditional and Complementary Medicine Practices in Rheumatoid Arthritis Patient Care. Mus Alparslan University The Journal of Health Sciences. 2024 ;4 (1), 49-57.
2. Brown P, Pratt AG, Hyrick K. Therapeutic Advances in Rheumatoid Arthritis. British Medical Journal., p:384; 2024.
3. Almutairi K, Nossent J, Preen D, Keen H, Inderjeeth C. The Global Prevalence of Rheumatoid Arthritis: a Meta-analysis Based on a Systematic Review. Rheumatology International. 2021; 41, 563-877.
4. Avanoğlu Güler A, Tufan A. Rheumatoid Arthritis and Comorbidities. (Editor: Ateş, A.) Rheumatoid Arthritis. 1st Edition. Ankara: Türkiye Klinikleri. 2020, 75-79.
5. Fernandez- Gonzalez M, Fernandez- Lao C, Martin L, Gonzales- Santy A, Lopez- Garzon M, Ortiz- Camino L, Lozeno M. Therapeutic Benefits of Balneotherapy on Quality of Life of Patients with Rheumatoid Arthritis: A Systematic Review. International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health. 2021, 18, 132.
6. Mutlu G, Türkmen M. The Use of Spring Water in Ancient Musculoskeletal Diseases and its Reflections on Today's Balneotherapy Practices. Journal of Historical Studies. 2020; 631-654.
7. Polat M. The Use of Geothermal Energy in Health.

- Multidisciplinary Perspective on Energy in Turkey. (Editor: Ataseven H, Ünsal DB.) Cumhuriyet University Press. Sivas. 2022, 41-51.
8. Kurt EE, Erdem HR, Tuncay F. Balneotherapy in Chronic Inflammatory Rheumatic Diseases: Review. *Journal of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation Science*. 2016; 19 (3), p:167-173.
 9. Koçyiğit BF, Sagtaganov Z, Yessirkepoz M, Akyol A. Assessment of Complementary and Alternative Medicine Methods in the Management of Ankylosing Spondylitis, Rheumatoid Arthritis and Fibromyalgia Syndrome. *Rheumatology International*. 2023; 43, 617-625.
 10. Dilekçi E, Özkuk K, Kaki B. Assessment of the Health Workers' Knowledge and Belief about Rheumatic and Musculoskeletal Diseases and SPA Treatments: A Descriptive Study. *Medicine Science International Medical Journal*. 2019; 8, (4), 901-907.
 11. Dilekçi E, Özkuk K, Kaki B. Assessment of the Knowledge and Behaviors of the Patients Undergoing Physical Therapy about Rheumatic Diseases and Spa Treatments. *Kocatepe Medical Journal*. 2022; 23, 12-18.
 12. Eyvaz N. Balneotherapy in Rheumatic Diseases. *Kocatepe Medical Journal*. 2020; 21, 129-135.
 13. Nacakoğlu I, Kaya E. Effects of Thermal Treatment on Anti-Rheumatoid Drug Cessation in Rheumatic Diseases. In the *Journal of Health Sciences of Kocaeli University*. 2020; 6 (2), 77-82.
 14. Santos I, Cantista P, Vasconcelas C. Balneotherapy in Rheumatoid Arthritis a Systematic Review. *International Journal of Biometeorology*. 2016; 60, 1287-1301.
 15. Karagülle M, Kardeş S, Dişçi R, Karagülle MZ. SPA Therapy Adjunct to Pharmacotherapy is Beneficial in Rheumatoid Arthritis: A Crossover Randomized Controlled Trial. *International Journal of Biometeorology*. 2018; 62, 195-205.
 16. Karagülle M, Kardeş S, Karagülle MZ. Long Term Efficacy of SPA Therapy in Patients with Rheumatoid Arthritis. *Rheumatology International*. 2018; 38, 352-362.
 17. Tognolo L, Loraci D, Fioravanti A, Tenti S, Scanu A, Magro G, Maccorone MC, Masiero S. Clinical Impact of Balneotherapy and Therapeutic Exercise in Rheumatic Diseases: A Lexical Analysis and Scoping Review. *Applied Sciences*. 2022, 1-14.
 18. Vergahen AP, Bierma Zeinstra SMA, Boers M, Cardoso JR, Lambeck J, De Bie R, De Vet HCW. Balneotherapy (or SPA Therapy) for Rheumatoid Arthritis. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*. 2017, 1-51.
 19. Cheleschi S, Tenti S, Seccafica I, Galvez I, Fioravanti A, Ortega E. Balneotherapy Year in Review 2021: Focus on the Mechanisms of Action of Balneotherapy in Rheumatic Diseases. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. 2022; 29, 8054-8073.
 20. Maccorone MC, Scanu A, Coraci D, Masiero S. The Potential Role of SPA Therapy in Managing Frailty in Rheumatic Patients: A Scoping Review. *Healthcare*. 2023; 11,1899.
 21. Sousa FI, Santos EJ, Cunha M, Ferreira RJ, Marques AA. Effectiveness of Nursing Consultations in People with Rheumatoid Arthritis: Systematic Review. *Revista de Enfermagem Referencia*. 2017, 148-155.
 22. Can G, Türker FZ. Nurses' Attitude Towards the Use of Complementary Approaches. *Journal of Integrative and Anatolian Medicine*.